

Modeling and Analysis of an SIRS Epidemic Model with Effect of Awareness Programs by Media

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Abstract : This paper proposes and analyzes an SIRS epidemic model incorporating the effects of the awareness programs driven by the media. Media plays a promising role in disseminating the information about outbreak of any disease across the globe. The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of the media on the spread and control of infectious diseases. This model is analyzed using stability theory of differential equations. The sensitivity of parameters has been discussed and it has been found that the awareness programs driven by the media have positive impact in reducing the infection prevalence of the infective population.

Keywords : Infectious diseases, SIRS model, Media, Stability theory, Simulation.

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